

Comparative taxonomy in *Justicia brandegeana* Wassh. & L.B. Sm, and *Justicia brasiliiana* Roth - newly introduced species to flora of Marathwada

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ABSTRACT

The aim was to study and identify morpho variations for taxonomy in the most morphological diverse genus *Justicia* L and its species. The most useful morphological characteristics that is the presence shape of flowers, presence of bilobed and trilobed corolla in the flowers of *Justicia* L species, which is closest to the genus like *Dicliptera*, *Andrograpis*, and *Lepidagathis*. The comparative morphological studies in *Justicia brandegeana* Wassh. & L.B. Sm, and *Justicia brasiliiana* Roth shown different morphological features proposed for the literature of *Justicia* L. for a future reference.

Keywords: *Justicia* L., Acanthaceae, Taxonomical Studies, *Justicia brasiliiana* Roth., *Justicia brandegeana*.

INTRODUCTION

In India there are 51 species and 5 varieties reported (S. Karthikeyan and *et.al.*,2009) of *Justicia* L. In the Maharashtra the genus of *Justicia* L has a 9 species were reported. (S. Karthikeyan and *et.al.*,2009). In the *Flora of Marathwada* 14 species was reported (Naik V.N 1998). Recently the genus was represented 70 species and 9 varieties in India (Arisdason *et al.*, 2020). In this study we described 2 species i.e. *Justicia brandegeana* Wassh. & L.B. Sm, and *Justicia brasiliiana* Roth. from the genus.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present study on the taxonomy of *Justicia* L is based on frequent visits to some local nurseries from Chh. Sambhajinagar district from August 2024 to December 2025. The collected plants are planted in different specialized areas in the gardens for further observations from vegetative and reproductive growth and examined the morphological characteristics at time to time from repeated visits. Morphological descriptions like leaf shape, size, floral characteristics, are assessed during the regular visits in gardens. After the dissection flowers, the taxonomic position was verified based on morphological features

compared with different flora. The proper identification of botanical names was validated by cross-referencing the

morphological description with all available records and published publications that are online; (www.powo.science.kew.org/). Voucher specimens were processed into mounted herbarium-sheets following Das (2021) and preserved in herbaria of Department of Botany, Deogiri College, Chh. Sambhajinagar.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

2 species belonging to the genus *Justicia* L. was observed with the morphological descriptions and used their diagnostic features for nomenclature.

***Justicia brandegeana* Wassh. & L.B. Sm:** Fl. Illustr. Catar. 1(Acantac.):102 (1969), *Beloperone guttata*, Brandege in Univ. Calif. Publ.Bot.4:278,(1912), *Calliaspidia guttata* (Brandege) Bremek. in Verh. Kon. Ned. Akad. Wetensch., Afd. Natuurk., Sect. 2. 45(2): 54,(1948), *Drejerella guttata* (Brandege) Bremek. in Philipp. J. Sci. 80: 14 (1952).

Common name: Mexican Shrimp Plant, Shrimp Plant, False Hop

An evergreen shrubby perennial, up to 1 -2 m high and wide with weak nodes branching stems. Stems and leaves downy. Lamina ovate-elliptic, usually 3-8 x 2-7 cm wide, entire, acute, base cuneate (Figure 1A). Flowers in subsessile or shortly pedunculate, cymes

from upper axils are located between the bracts in a spike inflorescence. Flowers usually 4-9 cm long. Bracteoles that resemble bracts imbricate, up to 2 cm long, elliptical, puberulent, and ciliate; colors range from red to purple to green. Calyx divided into 5-7 mm long lanceolate, acute puberulous lobes. Corolla up to 3-4 cm long with the upper lip, white with dark reddish or purple stripes on the lower lip, or entirely white-red lower lip, with hooded 2-lobed upper lip and spreading deep 3-lobed lower lip. 2 dark magenta-colored long filaments and a white colored stigma are attached inside the upper petals rugulae, stamens 2, held under upper lip, anthers bitheous, thecae at unequal height, style filiform, ovary superior, capsules oblong.

***Justicia brasiliiana* Roth :**

Beloperone amherstiae Nees in N.Wallich, Pl. Asiat. Rar. 3: 102 (1832), C.F.P.von Martius & auct. suc. (eds.), Fl.Bras.9:139(1847), *B.amherstiae* var. *debilis* Nees in C.F.P.von Martius & auct. suc. (eds.), Fl.Bras.9:139, (1847), *B.amherstiae graciliflora* Nees in C.F.P.von Martius & auct. suc. (eds.), Fl.Bras.9:139(1847), *B.amherstiae lanceolata* Nees in C.F.P.von Martius & auct. suc. (eds.), Fl. Bras. 9: 139 (1847), *B.cristata* Mart. Ex Nees in A.P.deCandolle, Prodr.11:419,1847), *Justicia nodosa* Hook. in Bot.Mag.56:t.2914, (1829), *Justicia temulenta* Nees in A.P.de Candolle, Prodr. 11: 419 (1847).

Fig. 1A *Justicia brandegeana* Wassh. & L.B. Sm
An evergreen herb perennial, up to 1 - 1.5 m height with weak nodes and branching stems. Stems rectangular and leaves downy, phyllotaxy opposite, lamina lanceolate or ovate-elliptic, usually 2 - 7 x 2 - 6 cm wide, entire, acute, base cuneate (Figure 1B), petiole 4 x 5 mm, flowers in subsessile, axillary or terminal, more than 3-6 flowers per nodes, cymes, from upper axils are located between the bracts in a spike inflorescence, flowers usually 2- 4 cm long. Bracts linear, green, bracteoles that resemble bracts imbricate, up to 2-5 mm long, elliptical and ciliate, Calyx 3-4, 2-5 mm long lanceolate, Corolla bilabiate, up to 4 cm long along the upper lip, pink with reddish stripes on the lower lip, or entirely red pink, with hooded 2-lobed upper lip and spreading 3-lobed lower lip, 2 dark magenta-colored filaments, white colored stigma are attached inside the upper petals of rugulae, stamens 2, held under upper lip, anthers bithecous, thecae at unequal heights. Style filiform, ovary superior, capsules panduriform, oblong, dry, dehiscent, 1 cm long, seeds 2-4 ovate, 2-4 mm long, dark black.

DISCUSSION

Justicia brandegeana Wassh. & L.B. Sm and *Justicia brasiliiana* Roth these 2 species belonging to the genus *Justicia* L. (Acanthaceae) have been widely used in traditional medicines and possess ornamental values in gardens as well. While these ornamental taxa have increased our floristic biodiversity of Marathwada

Fig. 1B) *Justicia brasiliiana* Roth.
adequate protection to these taxa is necessary to ensure their conservation particularly through cultivation.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable.

Correspondence and requests for materials should be addressed to **Ravi P. Patil**

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